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Self-Trapped Exciton Emission Under Ambient Conditions in Lead-Free Two-Dimensional Halide Double Perovskites Triggered by Heterovalent Metal Substitution

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Layered double halide perovskites possess a soft lattice and strong exciton-phonon interactions, which could, in principle, enable layered double halide perovskites to emerge as a new class of self-trapped exciton (STE) emitter materials. However, few layered double halide perovskites have been discovered with observable photoluminescence (PL) under room conditions, and this lack of observed PL is mainly due to the intrinsic parity-forbidden band transition. Herein, manganese ions (Mn^{2+}) are incorporated into $(PA)_4AgInBr_8$ ($PA = CH_3(CH_2)_2NH_3^+$) to form $(PA)_4Ag_{1-0.5x}Mn_xIn_{1-0.5x}Br_8$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1$) heterovalent-metal alloyed layered double perovskites. Oriented thin films are fabricated and investigated via X-ray diffraction $2\theta/\omega$ and ψ scan. With this alloy-induced extrinsic exciton self-trapping strategy, the dark STE state is made to be PL active, and broadband emission is obtained under room temperature conditions. Temperature-dependent PL gives insights into two emissive states and electron-phonon coupling strength. The associated Huang-Rhys factors and exciton binding energies quantitatively measure the excitonic localization in this quantum-well-like structure. This study demonstrates new approaches toward designing novel lead-free PL-active perovskites, which can broaden the library of PL-active 2D lead-free layered double halide perovskite phases.

Introduction

Two-dimensional (2D) hybrid perovskites have been widely investigated in optoelectronic devices, such as solar cells, light-emitting diodes, and photodetectors¹. Unlike three-dimensional (3D) perovskites, large and generally hydrophobic organic cation spacers are incorporated into the inorganic framework². Therefore, these materials have natural quantum well structures with strong exciton-phonon coupling effects and typically exhibit better chemical stability than their 3D counterparts³. Unfortunately, some barriers limit the commercialization of lead (Pb)-based 2D halide perovskites, including the formation of irreversible secondary Pb phases and high toxicity of Pb to the environment and human health⁴. As a result,

extensive efforts have been made to design stable and low-toxicity halide perovskites. Among them, halide 2D double perovskites with chemical formula $R_4MM'X_8$ (where R is a large organic cation, M and M' are monovalent and trivalent metal ions, and X is the halogen anion) have attracted much attention^{5,6}.

For these halide perovskites with a soft lattice, there is usually an in-gap state caused by lattice distortion, yielding the self-trapped exciton (STE) emission rather than a band-edge emission^{7,8}, but the STE emission is not typically observable under ambient conditions. Unlike Pb-based 2D perovskites with strong photoluminescence (PL) intensity⁹ or 3D colloidal perovskites with a high photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY)¹⁰, most 2D double perovskites exhibit unobservable PL at room temperature unless treated under extremely harsh conditions^{11,12}. The poor optoelectrical properties are proposed to be caused by the parity-forbidden transition band structure and dark STE states with a non-radiative recombination pathways¹³. The inactive STE emission for $(BA)_4AgBiBr_8$ was recovered by applying high pressures over 2.5 GPa, which can hinder the self-detrapping of excitons back to the free exciton states¹². Antimony (Sb^{3+}) was introduced to $(PEA)_4NaInCl_8$ to tune the dark STE states to bright states and achieved broadband emissions^{14,15}. However, it is still a challenge to obtain bright STE emissions under ambient conditions for 2D double perovskites, and the strategies to induce photoluminescence require in-depth investigation. For halide 2D double perovskites, the R, M, M', and X sites can be replaced to modulate the electronic band. Compared to a homovalent alloying strategy, heterovalent alloying in double perovskites exhibits a more

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distinct tunability of optoelectronic properties. Introducing manganese (Mn^{2+}) into octahedral layers is an effective method in 3D double^{16,17} and 2D lead-based¹⁸ perovskite nanocrystals to form a unique ${}^4\text{T}_1 \rightarrow {}^6\text{A}_1$ energy transition channel, achieving a highly efficient redshifted orange-red emission as well as enhanced PLQY. Mn^{2+} replacement is also considered insensitive to the host composition¹⁹.

In this work, we develop a series of bivalent-metal-alloyed 2D double perovskites to form a heterovalent metal system: $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{1-0.5x}\text{Mn}_x\text{In}_{1-0.5x}\text{Br}_8$ ($\text{Mn}_{0.2}$, $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$ and $\text{Mn}_{0.6}$ for $x = 0.2, 0.4$ and 0.6). To the best of our knowledge, there is no report on the luminescence of Mn^{2+} in heterovalent alloyed 2D double perovskites, especially for the Ag-In system with a larger band gap and lattice distortion compared with the Ag-Bi/Sb system, which makes the emission even harder^{20,21}. The impact of Mn^{2+} on optoelectronic properties and the correlation of exciton properties with energy transfer behaviour in 2D double perovskites will be investigated in this work, which can inform the development of additional PL-active, lead-free layered double halide perovskites.

Results and Discussions

The synthesis of 2D double perovskite films involved the dissolution of halide salts into the anhydrous DMSO solvent, followed by a one-step spin-coating process (see the Experimental Section in SI for details). The crystal structure of Mn-alloyed samples was identified by XRD. As depicted in Figure 1a, a typical layered structure was revealed by the out-of-plane $\{001\}$ diffraction patterns detected via

the $2\theta/\omega$ scan mode (Figure 1b). Here, organic layers of PA^+ cations cover the corner-shared metal-halide octahedral layers through hydrogen bonds and van der Waals forces. The interplanar distance of the $\{001\}$ crystal plane can be calculated via Bragg's Law (Table S1). We propose that the reason for subtle differences between the values of interplanar distance is octahedral layers with the largest centred ions (e.g. Ag^+) are distorted due to stressful compression of metal-halogen bonds. The stresses would be partially released by introducing ions with a smaller ionic radius (e.g. Mn^{2+}), and the vertical octahedral structure can recover the relaxed crystal structure. This result is consistent with the spacing expansion caused by Mn^{2+} substitution in different Ag-Mn-In mixed perovskites. The phase segregation occurs for less alloyed samples (e.g. $\text{Mn}_{0.2}$). Besides the $\{001\}$ crystal plane family, additional minor diffraction peaks are evident in several samples. We attribute this phenomenon to the nonuniform distribution of centred metal ions due to the large radius difference. Ions with a similar radius tend to stay together to form a relatively undistorted lattice. With the ratio of larger (Ag^+ : 115 pm) and smaller (e.g. Mn^{2+} : 70 pm and In^{3+} : 80 pm) ions getting far away, it is less likely to form a secondary phase. If the centred metal ion has a similar radius (e.g. $(\text{PA})_4\text{AgBiBr}_8$), the phase segregation can be avoided, as shown in Figure S1a. Similarly, based on the electronegativities of the metal elements (Ag: 1.93, Mn: 1.55, and In: 1.78), it is expected that the internally alloyed Mn likely occupies the octahedral $[\text{InX}_6]^{3-}$ sites in the form of $[\text{MnX}_6]^{4-}$. The SEM-EDS results further confirmed the replacement in Table S2. With the Mn^{2+} amount increasing, the atomic ratio of In^{3+} at most locations of different samples decreases due to gradual substitution by Mn^{2+} .

Figure 1. (a) Crystal structure of 2D double perovskite $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{1-0.5x}\text{Mn}_x\text{In}_{1-0.5x}\text{Br}_8$ (b) Out-of-plane XRD patterns of $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{1-0.5x}\text{Mn}_x\text{In}_{1-0.5x}\text{Br}_8$ through $2\theta/\omega$ scan mode and the enlarged part in the range of 13.5–15.5° (c) Diffraction intensity variation of $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{1-0.5x}\text{Mn}_x\text{In}_{1-0.5x}\text{Br}_8$

through ψ scan mode (d) GIXRD patterns of $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$ (e) Raman scattering micro-spectrum of $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{1-0.5x}\text{Mn}_x\text{In}_{1-0.5x}\text{Br}_8$ under 532 nm laser excitation

Going deeper, we further confirmed the uniform orientation of the {001} crystal plane through XRD in the ψ scan mode. With Ψ varying from 0 to 90° and 2θ fixed at (001), the curves in Figure 1c demonstrate a fast-declining signal with no intensity for $\Psi > 20^\circ$. This data indicates that the (001) plane only forms within a small angle window (0-15°) with the favourable orientation that grows parallel to the substrate at $\Psi = 0$. By varying Ψ step as shown in Figure S1b, no other plane orientation besides {001} was detected, which reveals a favourable layered structure of the layered 2D double perovskite materials. The crystal planes orthogonal to the diffraction plane were also investigated by grazing-incident X-ray diffraction (GIXRD) to obtain more information on these film samples (Figure 1d). The diffraction signal on the film sample surface was obtained with a small incident angle ($\theta < 3^\circ$). The diffraction peaks at 38.1° and 43.6° are attributed to the crystal plane existing within the octahedral layer ((220), (100), or (010)). These peaks disappear with $\theta > 5^\circ$ due to a reduced sample volume.

Dimension reduction in the layered structure emerged when the phonon behaviour was tracked via Raman scattering spectra (Figure 1e). No peaks were observed above 400 cm^{-1} . The peaks around 168 and 112 cm^{-1} (phonon energy 20.83 and 13.89 meV) are assigned to the A_{1g} and E_g modes, which are related to the symmetric and asymmetric stretching of the metal-halogen bonds in the octahedral layer^{22,23}. These phonon modes are located around 178 and 135 cm^{-1} for 3D perovskites due to the higher crystal stiffness. In the 2D counterparts, the loss of octahedral connectivity reduces the phonon

mode energy in the softened lattice, thus shifting the peaks to lower wavenumbers. Another high-energy feature at 300 cm^{-1} (phonon energy 37.19 meV), deviated from the second-order scattering of the A_{1g} mode, is regarded as a specific bending/rotational mode or PA-[MX] interaction²⁴. For the 2D double perovskite structure in this work, compared to single perovskite counterparts, the lattice dynamics analysis is more complicated due to the addition of two vibrating metal-halide sublattices. Beyond revealing the structural details, the intense Raman vibrational mode is an indicator of strong electron-phonon coupling of the lattice. This propensity to form local polarons influences the emissive behaviour, which will be probed in the temperature-dependent PL study. It should be noted that the Raman peak position shift from room temperature to low temperatures is small enough to allow comparison. Specifically, the difference is within 5 cm^{-1} (0.62 meV) for $(\text{PA})_4\text{AgBiBr}_8$ ¹¹.

To investigate the morphological characteristics, different spin-coating processes were attempted and optimized (Table S3), and the best-quality films are shown in Figures 2a and S2 via SEM. By introducing sufficient toluene as the antisolvent, crystal nucleation is facilitated, and the diffusion rate of the precursor during the annealing process is enhanced as well²⁵. Therefore, a dense, uniform, and pinhole-free film can be obtained with a grain size of less than 1 μm . Film roughness based on the best film quality was detected by AFM in Figures 2b and S2. The surfaces of all samples are smooth with moderate R_q values around 8 nm.

Figure 2. (a) SEM and (b) AFM image of $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$ (c) Optical absorption spectra for $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{1-0.5x}\text{Mn}_x\text{In}_{1-0.5x}\text{Br}_8$ (d) Steady-state PL spectra for $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{1-0.5x}\text{Mn}_x\text{In}_{1-0.5x}\text{Br}_8$ under room temperature. The laser excitation wavelength is 449 nm, and the laser power is 200 μW .

Next, we studied the room temperature optical properties of $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{1-0.5x}\text{Mn}_x\text{In}_{1-0.5x}\text{Br}_8$. The absorption spectra of $\text{Mn}_{0.2}$ and $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$ were probed using UV-vis diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (Figure 2c). $\text{Mn}_{0.2}$ and $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$ have an apparent excitonic absorption peak (288 nm) with a long absorption tail, demonstrating relatively large bandgaps (estimated as 3.35 eV for $\text{Mn}_{0.2}$ and 3.56 eV for $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$), as shown in Figure S3a. As the Mn^{2+} amount further increases, a blueshift of the absorption spectra and an increased bandgap value (3.62 eV for $\text{Mn}_{0.6}$) were observed based on the Tauc plot (Figure S3). As there is no overlap in the absorption peaks in the measurement range, the absorption transition pathway is an excitonic type (inorganic-to-inorganic transition) commonly related to octahedral metal orbitals¹⁴. PL spectra were recorded at room temperature under 449 nm excitation laser using 0.2 mW laser power (Figure 2d). We found $(\text{PA})_4\text{AgInBr}_8$ (Mn_0) exhibited no response, whereas two very broad features centred around 535 and 625 nm appeared in Mn-alloyed samples, accompanied by a large Stokes shift (over 200 nm). This is a unique characteristic of STE emission in halide perovskites^{26,27} rather than a narrow band edge emission. The peaks are centred around 534–541 nm (peak 2) and 622–625 nm (peak 1), respectively. The slight position variation indicates the modulation of the optical quality of the Mn dopant.

There are some reported broadband emissions of lead and lead-free perovskites caused by Mn dopants. The broadband emission of $(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2)\text{PbBr}_4$ includes a free-exciton emission at 418 nm and a STE emission at 540 nm, while an orange-red emission with a broad peak at 610 nm is found for Mn-doped $(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2)\text{PbBr}_4$ sample¹⁸. As the Mn^{2+} dopant concentration increases, the free-exciton and STE emission almost disappear while the Mn-Br state dominates. Similar Mn-Br emission is observed in another Mn-alloyed 2D double perovskite $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)\text{Pb}_{0.95}\text{Mn}_{0.05}\text{Br}_4$ at 640 nm²⁸. In some 3D Mn-doped samples (e.g. $\text{Mn-Cs}_2\text{Na}_x\text{Ag}_{1-x}\text{BiCl}_6$), two PL bands from the d-d state transition emission of Mn dopants (610 nm) and STEs states (585 nm) can be observed simultaneously as well²⁹, while in another system (e.g. $\text{Mn-Cs}_2\text{Na}_x\text{Ag}_{1-x}\text{InCl}_6$), STE states only play the role of bridge states and lead to the fast transfer of their energy to Mn states upon excitation¹⁷. Therefore, there is evidence that the PL emissions of Mn-doped samples do not exhibit STE emission. As we observed in Figures 2c and 2d, no additional characteristic peaks or apparent peak shifts appear in the absorption and emission spectra with Mn amount changing. Figure S4 exhibits an even shorter absorption tail for highly Mn-alloyed samples $\text{Mn}_{1.2}$ and $\text{Mn}_{1.4}$ with no other absorption contribution states. In contrast, additional features of 470 nm (430 nm) appeared in the absorption (PL excitation) spectra of highly Mn-doped $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2)\text{PbBr}_4$ sample, indicating a mid-gap state from the host depending on the Mn concentration³⁰. In that work, the Mn emission dominated with Mn concentration increasing,

and the emissive intensities of STE and free exciton peaks gradually decreased. A similar case happened in Mn-alloyed $\text{Cs}_2\text{Na}_x\text{Ag}_{1-x}\text{BiCl}_6$, where the Mn emission peak showed an enhanced intensity with Mn/Bi ratios from 0 to 1²⁹. In our case, we did not observe a competitive relation between STE and Mn emissions. The Mn emission that we try to predict here refers to the defect state of Mn-Br clusters, which we did not observe in this work. Therefore, we propose that these two emissive peaks are likely stem from similar intermediate energy state (STE emission), which is supported by detailed PL data in the following content. But we cannot exclude the role of other defects completely.

To obtain an in-depth understanding of the origin of the broadband emission, we investigated the temperature-dependent PL. PL mapping was conducted in the same area of $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}$ ($1 \mu\text{m}$ spot size) to obtain the average properties from the sample (Figures S5 and S6). Figures S5(a) and S6(a) exhibit the upper and lower boundary of all emission curves. The dark solid lines represent the average curves, which will be used in the following curve fitting process. This graph shows only slight variation in the peak position with changing temperature, indicating that excitons undergo similar emissive behaviour within this region. Figure 3a represents the average temperature-dependent PL spectrum from 4 to 300 K, which is the convolution of 3 Gaussian peaks at each temperature (Figure S7). However, peak 3 is a weak component that exists only at low temperatures, which we attribute to crystal imperfections, such as metal-halogen clusters or defects³¹. Since this emission is quenched at higher temperatures, we focus mainly on peaks 1 and 2. The suppression of non-radiative recombination at lower temperatures contributes to the stronger PL emission. No sharp characteristic of zero-phonon line (ZPL)³² is observed. Asymmetry and broadness of the line shape can reflect skewness in the sub-bands that are responsible for the emission caused by charge localization. Figure 3b shows the representative PL spectra of Mn-alloyed samples with different Mn concentrations at 4 K. Compared with room temperature spectra in Figure 2d, the intensity ratio of these two peaks is quite different. The intensity of peak 1 is higher than peak 2 at low temperatures, which might not be evidence of Mn centre emission due to a consistent Mn concentration regardless of the temperature change. Herein, we assume the PL emission is a phonon-assisted STE emissive process with different dominated phonon modes at different temperatures. All detected phonon modes were demonstrated via Raman spectra in Figure 1e, which is dominated by A_{1g} mode with two other less intense peaks at room temperature. However, this stretching mode can be weakened at lower temperatures due to phase transition^{11,33}, resulting in the dominant emission variation.

Figure 3. (a) Temperature-dependent PL spectra for $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$. (b) PL spectra for Mn_0 , $\text{Mn}_{0.2}$, $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$ and $\text{Mn}_{0.6}$ at 4K. Temperature-dependent PL FWHM of peak (c) 1 and (d) 2 for $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$ with corresponding fitted curves (e) TRPL spectrum for $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$ with corresponding fitted decay curves (f) Schematic diagram of proposed energy transfer model of $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{1-0.5x}\text{Mn}_x\text{In}_{1-0.5x}\text{Br}_8$ 2D double perovskites

The formation of STEs strongly relates to strong electron–phonon coupling effects causing local distortions in the soft lattice of 2D perovskites. The emission of phonons can vary the energy transitions and broaden sharp transitions into wide bands. The approximation to the electron–phonon coupling strength was first introduced via an expression (Poisson distribution), which represents the transition probability between the initial and final excited band state^{34–36}:

$$W_p = \frac{S^p e^{-S}}{p!} \quad (1)$$

where p is the number of vibrational quanta (phonons) excited in the transition. This leads to an absorption spectrum consisting of a series of lines at

$$E_p = E_{\text{ZPL}} \pm p\hbar\omega_{\text{ph}} \quad (2)$$

In the simplistic situation ($T = 0$ K and dispersion-less phonon frequencies), optical transitions occur at energies E_p with $p = 0, 1, 2$, etc. In the Born-Oppenheimer approximation, W_p indicates the overlapping integration of the phonon wave function that depends on the relative lattice displacement³⁴. Note that in the case of a finite W_p value (an infinitesimal S value), the spectrum becomes a single unbroadened line with almost full overlapping of wave functions at the static lattice position. For a higher S value (lower W_p value), it is less likely to generate ZPL due to less wave function overlap, resulting in a broadened Gaussian line shape.

The effective phonon energy can be connected with different full width at half-maximum (FWHM) values under variant temperatures, as described by the Toyozawa equation:^{37,38}

$$\text{FWHM} = 2.36\sqrt{S}\hbar\omega_{\text{ph}} \sqrt{\coth \frac{\hbar\omega_{\text{ph}}}{2k_{\text{B}}T}} \quad (3)$$

where S is the Huang–Rhys factor to evaluate the electron–phonon interaction strength, \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, ω_{ph} is the phonon frequency, $\hbar\omega_{\text{ph}}$ is the effective phonon energy, k_{B} is the Boltzmann constant, and T is the temperature. A large but appropriate S indicates a high possibility of the formation of STEs. Exceeded S value could lead to the strong lattice vibration with PL quenching²⁴.

For peak 1, fitting FWHM with temperature in Figure 3c yields a coupling parameter S_1 of 26.30 ± 4.19 and an effective phonon energy $\hbar\omega_{\text{ph}1}$ of 14.31 ± 1.27 meV. This value agrees with the E_{g} mode of 13.89 meV observed in the Raman spectrum of $\text{Mn}_{0.4}$. However, this behaviour maintains only up to around 100 K, after which another phonon mode dominates. The data points evolve with a lesser slope with increasing temperature after 100 K. Another fitting curve generates a coupling parameter $S_2 = 5.83 \pm 1.48$ and an effective phonon energy of $\hbar\omega_{\text{ph}2} = 37.16 \pm 6.16$ meV. This value likely corresponds to the higher energy phonon mode of 37.19 meV in the Raman spectrum. If the peak 2 FWHM is fitted based on temperature like in Figure 3d, the coupling parameters S_1 and S_2 are similar between each temperature region, 16.96 ± 5.82 and $15.69 \pm$

5.44, respectively. The effective phonon energy $\hbar\omega_{\text{ph}}$ are 18.37 ± 3.41 and 17.82 ± 3.94 meV, respectively, corresponding to the A_{1g} mode of 20.83 meV consistently observed in the Raman spectrum. Any significant change of the S value with temperature reflects the variation of the effective phonon energy. The coupling parameter S represents the phonon number of a single energy emitted as the charge carrier relaxes; thus, higher energy phonons decrease the phonon number (smaller S) required for the same emission³⁴. Based on the previous hypothesis, E_g and another higher energy phonon mode dominate under low temperatures, with a fast-declining trend at room temperature, which could explain why the intensity of peak 1 is higher than peak 2 at low temperatures. Meanwhile, the intensity of peak 2 does not change too much from 4 to 300 K because of the steady A_{1g} mode. The S value is large enough to indicate that the coupling is quite strong and that phonon-assisted STE recombination is responsible for the broadband emission. For example, S for ZnSe and CsPbBr₃ is only 0.31³⁹ and 0.23⁴⁰, but S for Cs₂AgIn_{0.9}Bi_{0.1}Cl₆ nanoplatelets and CsCu₂I₃ is 33⁴¹ and 38⁴². Such a large S factor indicates a strong electron-phonon coupling, and the low crystal dimensionality can promote octahedral distortion and STEs formation. The dominant phonon modes dictate the shift of PL peak position of the two bands that experience different skewness: redshift then blueshift with increasing temperature for peak 1 but no obvious variation for peak 2. Further evidence of the emission origin based on STE emission is confirmed in the time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) signal. The PL intensity decay time and fitted curves of these two peaks are shown in Figure 3e. The lifetimes for peaks 1 and 2 can be well-fitted by a single exponential function:

$$y = y_0 + Ae^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \quad (4)$$

Two peaks exhibit very similar PL decay with average lifetime τ of ≈ 3 and 4 ns in the same order of magnitude, suggesting that they originate from homogeneous excited states rather than an energy-transfer process between two distinct states.

Here, we use a configurational coordinate diagram (Figure 3f) to propose the energy transfer model, including two phonon-assisted STE emissions colored in orange and green (STE1 and STE2). The lower band is the valence band, the upper band is the STE band, and the intermediate band is another STE band. The conduction band (not shown) should lie above the STE band. The absorption pathway is from A to B, and STE emission is from C to D (and E to F). The energy E_{ZPL} is known as the ZPL of the emission band, as it is the direct radiative transition from emission to absorption edge. Higher-energy absorption bands are possible with the phonon emission energy E_{ph} as the charge carrier relaxes from point B to C. Similarly, the emissive pathway from C to D (and E to F) is accompanied by emitted phonons as the charge carriers relax back to the valence band.

Moreover, to illustrate the quenching of the PL intensity with increasing temperature, the Arrhenius formula is used:^{24,38}

$$I(T) = \frac{I_0}{1 + Ae^{-E_b/k_B T}} \quad (5)$$

where I_0 is the intensity at 0 K. E_b is the exciton binding energy, and k_B is the Boltzmann constant.

The calculated binding energies, E_b , of peaks 1 and 2 are 284.38 ± 34.33 and 171.91 ± 60.2 meV, respectively (Figure S8), which is much larger than room-temperature thermal energy (~ 26 meV) and implies high localization effects. In 2D perovskites, exciton states can be regarded as Wannier type in the inorganic layer or Frenkel type across the layers^{43,44}. Exciton size differences result in distinct exciton binding energies: Typically, Wannier excitons have small binding energies (~ 100 meV), whereas Frenkel excitons have large ($\sim 500+$ meV) binding energies. Given the intrinsic softness of the 2D perovskites, lattice dynamic evolution may cause temperature-dependent and time-dependent localization effects, which can regulate the exciton property^{45,46}. Therefore, it is reasonable that excitons in 2D perovskites exhibit the behaviour of both types of excitons⁴⁶. We hypothesize our exciton character falls between the Wannier and Frenkel regimes. The dependence of the PL intensity on the laser power is plotted in Figure S9 with a logarithmic scale, which is given by the power law coefficient, described by the slope of the fitting line (0.69 and 0.61 here). Usually, excitonic PL emission increases superlinearly with the laser power, where the slope is in the range of 1 to 2. For donor-acceptor pair or free-to-bound transitions, the PL intensity increases sublinearly with a slope of less than 1⁴⁷. However, the influence of strong electron-phonon coupling can render this recombination pathway unreliable when the excitons are heavily localized by small polarons in the lattice, causing severe restrictions on recombination at specific locations in the lattice. Such interactions violate the power law model, which does not consider localization effects in the case of excitonic emission²⁴. Thus, excitonic emission cannot be excluded based on the power-dependent integrated PL intensity data alone. Temperature-dependent and Mn-concentration-dependent PL spectra demonstrate different dominant emission peaks with temperature changes, suggesting that phonon-assisted STE emission is more likely over Mn-center emission. Huang–Rhys factor calculation and TRPL spectra further verify the emissions likely originate from homogeneous excited states with no energy transfer between two distinct states.

Halogen substitution was applied to further characterize tunable optoelectronic properties of 2D halide double perovskites. The replacement of iodine did not affect the layered crystal structure, but a degree of phase segregation was observed for samples with partial iodine mixing (Figure 4a). Atoms with a larger radius may compensate for the lattice strain and avoid the secondary phase formation. The excitonic absorption peak of iodine-mixed samples is not obvious in the measurement range. We can observe an increased trend for bandgap with the addition of iodine in Figure S3b. The PL spectrum displays a blueshift as bromine is gradually replaced by iodine, which is the opposite trend for the band-edge emission of perovskites that typically leads to a strong redshift⁹. Thus, we further confirm that the broadband emission is derived from the activated intermediate state. The chemistry of triggering broadband emissions under room conditions can be extended to other hybrid halide perovskites.

Figure 4. (a) Out-of-plane XRD patterns (b) Optical absorption spectra (c) Steady-state PL spectra for $(\text{PA})_4\text{Ag}_{0.8}\text{Mn}_{0.4}\text{In}_{0.8}\text{Br}_{8-y}\text{I}_y$ (I_0 , I_2 and I_4 for $y=0, 2$ and 4)

Conclusions

We successfully synthesized a series of heterovalent-metal alloyed Ag-Mn-In layered double perovskites. The thin films crystalize as highly oriented structures on the substrate surface. With the introduction of Mn^{2+} , the parity-forbidden band transition is broken, and broadband emission is obtained under room conditions. Characterization of the temperature-dependent and Mn-concentration-dependent PL emission leads us to propose that two active STE emission centres coexist within the bandgap. The electron-phonon coupling calculation demonstrates a high Huang-Rhys factor value and its variation with different temperature ranges, suggesting strong phonon-assisted STE emission. PL decay curves suggest that two emissions originate from similar excited states. The configurational coordinate model illustrates the proposed energy transfer process from STE states. This study may inspire the design of PL-active ionic halide perovskites and help us understand the correlation of exciton properties with energy transfer behaviour in 2D double perovskites.

Author contributions

Chunyang Chi: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, validation, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing. Yi Wei Ho: data curation, formal analysis, investigation. Andres Granados del Aguila: data curation, formal analysis, investigation. Yue Xu: investigation. Yehonadav Bekenstein: methodology. Silvija Gradecak-Garaj: methodology. Maciej Koperski: methodology, project administration. Andrew B. Wong: conceptualization, funding acquisition, methodology, project administration, resources, supervision, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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